

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4294364

Hygiene Practices and its Implications on Public Health among Food Handlers in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine the hygiene practices among University food handlers in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. A cross-sectional descriptive study design was adopted using 135 food handlers who were randomly selected. Data were collected using a 26-item structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed using simple percentage. Findings from this study revealed that a vast majority of food vendors were not consistent in strictly adhering to standard hygiene practices thus, predisposing consumers to various health risks. Factors adversely affecting recommended hygiene practices among food vendors include lack of basic hygiene knowledge, employment of cheap and unskilled workers and lack of training and retraining programmes for food vendors among others. The study recommended periodic food safety training sessions for food handlers to increase their awareness on food safety. The activities of the food handlers should be regularly monitored and appropriate actions taken by health officers to ensuring that food safety procedures are followed accordingly.

Keywords: hygiene, practices, implications, public health, food handlers